

Assessment of the Challenges and Prospects of Performative Pedagogy in Secondary School Classrooms in Kontagora Local Government Area

¹Ebohon Godfrey Oghuan, ²Ass. Prof. Daniel James Chikada &
²Ass. Prof. Sunday Ogbu Igbaba

Corresponding Author: ebohongodfrey999@gmail.com

¹English Department, Federal University of Education Kontagora, Niger State

²Department of Theatre and Cultural Studies, Faculty of Arts Nasarawa State University, Keffi

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.21115347>

Abstract

This study assessed the challenges and prospects of performative pedagogy in secondary school classrooms in Kontagora Local Government Area. The study was motivated by the growing need for learner-centered instructional approaches that enhance student engagement, creativity, and academic performance in secondary education. Two specific objectives guided the study: to examine the challenges affecting the implementation of performative pedagogy and to assess its prospects and potential benefits in improving teaching and learning outcomes. A descriptive survey research design was adopted, and data were collected using a structured questionnaire administered to 399 respondents, out of which 379 were correctly filled and returned. The findings revealed a negative and insignificant relationship between the identified challenges and the implementation of performative pedagogy in secondary schools in Kontagora Local Government Area. The respondents generally disagreed that factors such as inadequate teacher training, overcrowded classrooms, lack of instructional materials, examination-oriented teaching, and poor institutional support significantly hinder the implementation of performative pedagogy. The findings revealed a positive and significant relationship between performative pedagogy and improved teaching effectiveness and student learning outcomes in secondary schools in Kontagora Local Government Area. This shows that performative pedagogy has strong educational benefits when applied in secondary school classrooms. The study concludes that performative pedagogy remains a viable and beneficial instructional approach despite existing challenges in the education system. It recommends continuous teacher training, improved instructional resources, and supportive school environments to enhance the effective implementation of performative pedagogy in secondary schools.

Keywords: Performative pedagogy, classroom teaching, secondary schools, student engagement, instructional methods

Introduction

Traditional instructional methods, particularly those characterized by teacher dominance and rote memorization, are increasingly being criticized for their inability to equip learners with critical thinking, creativity, and problem-solving skills required in the twenty-first century. As a result, educators and policymakers are shifting attention toward participatory and experiential teaching strategies that promote active engagement in the learning process. One such emerging approach is performative pedagogy, which integrates performance-based techniques such as drama, role-play, storytelling, and simulation into classroom instruction. This approach reflects a paradigm shift from passive learning to active knowledge construction, thereby aligning with modern educational philosophies. Despite its pedagogical advantages, the implementation of performative pedagogy in secondary schools, particularly within developing countries such as Nigeria, remains fraught with challenges. Consequently, many teachers continue to rely on conventional lecture-based approaches, which limit student participation and creativity. Ogunyemi (2018), observes that systemic constraints, including rigid curricula and inadequate teacher preparation, hinder the effective integration of innovative pedagogies in Nigerian classrooms.

Within Kontagora Local Government Area, these challenges are further exacerbated by contextual realities such as limited resources, inadequate infrastructure, and large class sizes. Many secondary schools in the area operate under conditions that are not conducive to the implementation of performative teaching methods. For example, overcrowded classrooms make it difficult for teachers to organize interactive activities, while the lack of instructional materials restricts the scope of performance-based learning. Additionally, insufficient funding and limited access to professional development programs reduce teachers' capacity to adopt and sustain innovative pedagogical practices (Olaifa et al, 2025).

Furthermore, the absence of clear policy guidelines supporting the use of performative pedagogy contributes to its limited adoption in secondary schools. Although the Federal Ministry of Education in Nigeria has introduced reforms aimed at promoting learner-centered education, the translation of these policies into classroom practice remains inconsistent. This finding is consistent with the study of Onyekwelu (2024), who observed that despite ongoing educational reforms, many Nigerian teachers continue to rely on traditional instructional approaches due to examination pressures, inadequate support systems, and limited opportunities for professional development. Similarly,

Universal Basic Education Commission reports have highlighted the persistent gap between educational policy objectives and actual classroom practices, particularly regarding the implementation of learner-centered pedagogies.

The increasing global emphasis on competency-based education and the development of twenty-first-century skills provides a strong rationale for integrating performance-based learning into the curriculum. Technological advancements also present new opportunities for enhancing performative pedagogy through digital storytelling, virtual simulations, and multimedia presentations. These tools can help overcome some of the resource limitations faced by schools and make learning more interactive and engaging. This position is supported by Akinsanoye (2025), who argued that contemporary education requires constructivist and learner-centred approaches that promote critical thinking, collaboration, creativity, and other twenty-first-century competencies. Similarly, Asuquo et al, (2024) observed that digital technologies create more engaging and interactive learning experiences and can significantly improve teaching and learning outcomes when effectively integrated into secondary education. Furthermore, Apata (2023) noted that technology-enhanced pedagogical practices provide opportunities for interactive instruction, learner participation, and the development of digital skills necessary for the twenty-first century, although adequate infrastructure and teacher training remain essential for successful implementation. Adeyemi and Okebukola (2019) examined the effectiveness of drama-based instructional strategies in enhancing students' academic achievement in secondary school English Language in Nigeria. The study adopted a quasi-experimental research design involving pre-test and post-test control groups across selected secondary schools in southwestern Nigeria. Data were analyzed using t-test statistics. The findings revealed that students taught using drama-based (performative) methods performed significantly better than those taught using traditional lecture methods. However, the study also identified challenges such as large class sizes and inadequate instructional time, which limited the effective application of performative techniques in classroom settings.

Odeh and Eze (2020) conducted a study aimed at investigating teachers' perceptions and readiness to adopt performative pedagogy in teaching social studies in Nigerian secondary schools. The study employed a descriptive survey research design, using structured questionnaires administered to teachers in selected schools in Enugu State. Data were analyzed using mean scores and standard

deviation. The findings showed that while teachers recognized the benefits of performative pedagogy in improving student engagement, many lacked adequate training and institutional support.

In another study, Bamgbose and Salawu (2021) examined the impact of role-play and simulation strategies on students' critical thinking skills in civic education. The study adopted a mixed-method approach, combining quantitative test scores with qualitative interviews. The sample included secondary school students in Ogun State, Nigeria. Statistical analysis using ANCOVA indicated that students exposed to performative teaching strategies demonstrated higher critical thinking abilities compared to those in conventional classrooms. However, the study reported constraints such as lack of teaching materials and insufficient teacher training, which hindered wider adoption of performative pedagogy. Furthermore, Ibrahim and Mohammed (2022) investigated the challenges and prospects of innovative teaching methods, including performative pedagogy, in science education in northern Nigeria. The study used a survey research design involving science teachers from public secondary schools. Data were collected through questionnaires and analyzed using descriptive statistics. The findings revealed that although teachers acknowledged the potential of performative pedagogy to improve understanding of abstract scientific concepts, its implementation was limited by overcrowded classrooms, inadequate laboratory facilities, and lack of professional development opportunities.

The implementation of performative pedagogy in Nigeria is constrained by deep-rooted structural and conceptual issues within the educational system. At the core of these challenges is the persistence of traditional, teacher-centered instructional methods that prioritize rote learning and examination performance over active, experiential learning. Performative pedagogy, which emphasizes participation, creativity, and embodied learning, requires a fundamental shift in instructional orientation—one that many teachers find difficult to adopt due to long-standing pedagogical traditions. As Dewey (1938) argues, meaningful education is grounded in experience and interaction; however, in the Nigerian context, the dominance of content-driven teaching limits the practical realization of such approaches

Infrastructural limitations, teachers' attitudes and perceptions further complicate the adoption of performative pedagogy in Nigeria. Many public secondary schools operate under challenging conditions, including overcrowded classrooms, insufficient teaching materials, and rigid curricular

structures. These constraints hinder the organization of interactive and performance-based activities, which often require space, time, and flexibility. Ogunyemi, (2018) notes that systemic inefficiencies and limited resources continue to impede pedagogical innovation in Nigerian schools. Furthermore, cultural resistance to change and limited awareness of the benefits of performance-based learning contribute to the slow adoption of this pedagogical approach across the country (Gallagher and Booth 2003). In summary, the challenges affecting the implementation of performative pedagogy in Nigeria are multifaceted, encompassing pedagogical, institutional, and attitudinal dimensions. Addressing these barriers requires comprehensive reforms in teacher education, curriculum design, and educational policy, alongside increased investment in school infrastructure and professional development. Only through such coordinated efforts can performative pedagogy be effectively integrated into Nigerian classrooms to enhance teaching and learning outcomes.

Prospects and Potential Benefits of Adopting Performative Pedagogy in Nigeria

As the education system continues to shift toward learner-centered approaches, performative pedagogy offers a viable alternative to traditional rote learning methods that have long dominated classroom instruction. This approach, which emphasizes drama, role-play, storytelling, simulation, and embodied learning, enhances student participation and encourages active knowledge construction. According to Dewey, (1938) education becomes most meaningful when learners engage directly with experiences that stimulate reflection and inquiry, thereby improving understanding and retention.

One of the major benefits of performative pedagogy is its ability to enhance student engagement and motivation. By transforming passive learners into active participants, it fosters curiosity, creativity, and collaboration in the classroom. Students are given opportunities to express ideas, interpret concepts, and work collectively, which strengthens communication skills and critical thinking abilities. In line with the sociocultural theory of Vygotsky, (1978), learning is most effective when it occurs through social interaction and shared experiences, making performative pedagogy particularly relevant in diverse classroom settings. The approach also has the potential to bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical application. In many Nigerian schools, students often struggle to connect classroom content with real-world experiences. Performative pedagogy addresses this challenge by simulating real-life scenarios, enabling learners to apply theoretical concepts in practical

contexts. This not only deepens understanding but also prepares students for real-world problem-solving situations. As Dewey (1938) emphasizes, education should prepare learners for life through active engagement rather than passive memorization.

Performative pedagogy refers to a learner-centred instructional approach that employs performance, improvisation, role-play, dramatization, and other participatory learning activities to facilitate experiential learning, critical thinking, creativity, collaboration, and active knowledge construction among learners (Ogunkunbi and Adejare, (2025); Akinsola, (2024). Oluwatoyin and Aderonke (2025), sees performative pedagogy as a teaching approach that utilizes theatrical techniques, improvisation, enactment, and participatory performance to engage learners in the active construction of knowledge while fostering creativity, communication, reflection, and problem-solving skills.

Akinsola (2024) views performative pedagogy as an experiential and interactive instructional process through which learners acquire knowledge, values, and skills by participating in drama-based and performance-oriented activities that encourage collaboration, self-expression, and meaningful engagement with learning content.

The theoretical foundation guiding this study is the Constructivist Learning Theory, which provides a strong explanatory lens for understanding performative pedagogy in secondary school classrooms. Constructivism is primarily associated with the works of Jean Piaget (1952) and Lev Vygotsky (1978). Although both scholars developed their ideas independently, their contributions collectively form the intellectual basis for modern constructivist thought in education.

Piaget's constructivist perspective is rooted in the assumption that learners are active participants in the learning process. According to his theory, knowledge is not passively received but actively built through processes of assimilation and accommodation as learners interact with their environment (Piaget 1970). His motivation was to understand how children develop logical thinking and intellectual structures over time. He argued that cognitive development occurs in stages, and effective learning happens when instructional activities align with the learner's developmental stage. This implies that learners in secondary schools benefit more from interactive and hands-on learning experiences rather than passive lecture-based instruction. On the other hand, Vygotsky, (1978), expanded constructivism by introducing the sociocultural dimension of learning. His central assumption is that learning is fundamentally a social process, shaped by interaction with more

knowledgeable others, such as teachers and peers. He introduced the concept of the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD), which refers to the gap between what learners can do independently and what they can achieve with. His motivation was to explain how culture, language, and social interaction influence cognitive development. This perspective strongly supports collaborative and participatory learning approaches, which are central to performative pedagogy.

Constructivist theory assumes that learners construct meaning actively rather than simply absorbing information from teachers. It also assumes that knowledge is context-dependent and best learned through authentic experiences. In classroom practice, this translates into learner-centered approaches such as discussion, role-play, dramatization, simulation, and group activities all of which are core elements of performative pedagogy. Teachers under this framework act as facilitators rather than sole transmitters of knowledge, guiding learners as they construct understanding through interaction and reflection. Despite its strong educational value, constructivism has attracted several critiques. One major criticism is that it places heavy demands on teachers in terms of planning, classroom management, and instructional flexibility. Critics argue that in large classrooms, such as those common in Nigerian secondary schools, it may be difficult to effectively implement constructivist strategies. Others contend that constructivism may lead to gaps in foundational knowledge if learners are not properly guided, especially in subject areas that require structured learning. Additionally, some educational psychologists argue that the theory underestimates the importance of direct instruction in certain contexts where efficiency and clarity are required.

The relevance of Constructivist Learning Theory to this study is significant. The focus of this research directly aligns with constructivist principles. Performative pedagogy is inherently constructivist because it emphasizes active student participation, collaboration, and experiential learning. Through activities such as dramatization and role-play, students construct knowledge by engaging with content in meaningful and contextualized ways. Conversely, the prospects such as improved engagement, critical thinking, and deeper understanding reflect the positive outcomes predicted by constructivist learning principles. The theory also justifies the shift from teacher-centered to learner-centered instruction, which is central to educational reform efforts in Nigeria.

Ongoing educational reforms in Nigeria aimed at improving teaching quality and learning outcomes provide a supportive framework for the adoption of innovative pedagogies. Initiatives focused on

teacher training, curriculum development, and the integration of creative arts into education can facilitate the implementation of performative pedagogy. Collaborative efforts among stakeholders including educators, policymakers, and community members are essential for creating an enabling environment that supports pedagogical innovation. As schools in Kontagora Local Government Area strive to improve educational outcomes, the adoption of performative pedagogy presents a viable strategy for achieving these objectives.

Research Objectives

The following are the objectives of the study;

1. To examine the key challenges affecting the implementation of performative pedagogy in classroom teaching and learning in secondary schools in Kontagora Local Government Area
2. Assess the prospects of adopting performative pedagogy for improving teaching effectiveness and student learning outcomes in secondary schools in Kontagora Local Government Area

Research Questions

1. What are the Challenges to the Implementation of Performative Pedagogy
2. What are the Prospects and Benefits of Performative Pedagogy

Methodology

The study adopt a descriptive survey research design, which is considered appropriate for collecting and analyzing data on the challenges and prospects of performative pedagogy in secondary school classrooms in Kontagora Local Government Area. The ten schools are as follow; UBE Model Science College, Kontagora, Day Secondary School, Sabon Kasuwa, Day Secondary School Tukura, Women Day College, Kontagora, Day Secondary School Tunganwawa, Day Secondary School, Rafingora, Day Secondary, Masuga, Day Secondary school, Madara, Government Technical College, Kontagora and Saidu Namaska Junior Secondary School, Kontagora .

This design allows the researcher to obtain information from a large group of respondents in their natural setting without manipulating any variables. The population of the study consist 1987 secondary school teachers and students in selected public schools within the study area, simple random technique was used to select 399 respondents. A structured questionnaire is the primary instrument for data collection. The questionnaire was designed using a Likert scale format (Strongly Agree to Strongly Disagree) to capture respondents' views on the implementation challenges and

perceived benefits of performative pedagogy. The instrument is divided into sections covering demographic information, challenges affecting implementation, and prospects of performative pedagogy. The questionnaire is also validated by experts in educational research to ensure clarity, relevance, and content validity. A pilot test was conducted in a Magama local government area to determine the reliability of the instrument using Cronbach's Alpha method with the reliability coefficient of 0.78. Questionnaire was administered directly to respondents by the researcher. The collected data was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts, percentages, and mean scores to answer the research questions. This method ensures that the study captures accurate and reliable perceptions of teachers regarding performative pedagogy in secondary schools.

Result

Research Question One: What Are the Challenges Affecting the Implementation of Performative Pedagogy

This sought to examine the challenges affecting the implementation of performative pedagogy in classroom teaching and learning in secondary schools in Kontagora Local Government Area. Data were collected using a five-point Likert scale questionnaire, and responses were analysed using the Average Weighted Mean (AWM) and the Standard Deviation (Std. Dev). The AWM was used to determine the central tendency of responses, while the Standard Deviation measured the degree of dispersion or variability among respondents. The decision to accept or reject each item was guided by a 0.80 interval criterion, where an AWM of 1.80 to 2.59 corresponds to a "Disagree" rating.

Table 1: Respondents' Views on Challenges to the Implementation of Performative Pedagogy

S/N	Questionnaire Items	AWM	Std. Dev	Decision
1	Inadequate teacher training affects the implementation of performative pedagogy.	2.53	1.34	Disagree
2	Overcrowded classrooms hinder the use of performative teaching methods.	2.52	1.31	Disagree
3	Lack of instructional materials affects the effective use of performative pedagogy.	2.55	1.36	Disagree
4	Examination-oriented teaching discourages performative classroom activities.	2.53	1.31	Disagree
5	Poor institutional support affects the adoption of performative pedagogy.	2.51	1.33	Disagree

The findings presented in Table 1 reveal a notable pattern: respondents disagreed that the identified factors constitute significant challenges to the implementation of performative pedagogy in secondary schools in Kontagora LGA. The AWM scores for all five items ranged narrowly between 2.51 and 2.55, all falling within the “Disagree” decision band. This consistency across items indicates a shared perception among the respondents that these commonly assumed barriers do not significantly impede the adoption of performative pedagogy in their specific educational context. The accompanying standard deviation values, which ranged from 1.31 to 1.36, point to a moderate level of variability in the responses. This degree of spread suggests that while the majority of respondents rejected these factors as major obstacles, a considerable minority held divergent views, indicating that individual experiences and school contexts may have influenced how respondents assessed the severity of these challenges.

Specifically, respondents disagreed that inadequate teacher training (AWM = 2.53, Std. Dev = 1.34), overcrowded classrooms (AWM = 2.52, Std. Dev = 1.31), lack of instructional materials (AWM = 2.55, Std. Dev = 1.36), examination-oriented teaching culture (AWM = 2.53, Std. Dev = 1.31), and poor institutional support (AWM = 2.51, Std. Dev = 1.33) are major hindrances to performative teaching in their schools. The standard deviation for lack of instructional materials was the highest (1.36), suggesting that this particular item generated the widest spread of opinion among respondents and may be a more contested issue across different school settings. Conversely, items relating to overcrowded classrooms and examination-oriented teaching recorded the lowest standard deviations (1.31), reflecting relatively more uniform disagreement on those points. Taken together, these results suggest that teachers and school administrators in Kontagora Local Government Area may possess sufficient professional competence and institutional awareness to integrate performative strategies into their practice, regardless of prevailing resource constraints. The findings further imply that performative pedagogy is perceived as sufficiently flexible and adaptable to the realities of the local school environment, which is significant in the context of this study’s first objective, as it challenges widely held assumptions about infrastructural barriers and instead points to an enabling disposition among practitioners toward performative approaches to teaching and learning.

Research Question Two: Prospects and Benefits of Performative Pedagogy

Respondents' views were measured using the same five-point Likert scale instrument, and both the AWM and Standard Deviation were computed to capture the strength and consistency of their responses, with an AWM of 3.40 to 4.19 interpreted as "Agree."

Table 2: Respondents' Views on the Prospects and Benefits of Performative Pedagogy

S/N	Questionnaire Items	AWM	Std. Dev	Decision
1	Performative pedagogy improves students' classroom participation.	3.85	1.26	Agree
2	Performative pedagogy enhances students' critical thinking ability.	3.84	1.28	Agree
3	The use of performative pedagogy increases students' academic performance.	3.83	1.27	Agree
4	Performative pedagogy promotes creativity and collaboration among students.	3.85	1.29	Agree
5	Performative pedagogy makes classroom teaching more interactive and effective.	3.87	1.26	Agree

The data presented in Table 2 reflect a strong and consistent positive consensus among respondents regarding the educational value of performative pedagogy. All five items recorded AWM scores between 3.83 and 3.87, placing each firmly within the "Agree" decision band. The high degree of agreement across all items signals a broadly shared conviction among teachers and stakeholders in Kontagora Local Government Area that performative pedagogy holds considerable promise for transforming teaching and learning outcomes at the secondary school level. The standard deviation values for all items fell within a narrow range of 1.26 to 1.29, indicating a relatively consistent pattern of agreement among respondents. The low variability further strengthens the credibility of these findings, as it suggests that the positive perception of performative pedagogy is not isolated to a few individuals but is broadly shared across the study population.

Respondents agreed that performative pedagogy improves students' classroom participation (AWM = 3.85, Std. Dev = 1.26), enhances critical thinking ability (AWM = 3.84, Std. Dev = 1.28), increases academic performance (AWM = 3.83, Std. Dev = 1.27), promotes creativity and collaboration (AWM = 3.85, Std. Dev = 1.29), and makes classroom teaching more interactive and effective (AWM = 3.87, Std. Dev = 1.26). The highest-rated item, which affirms that performative pedagogy makes teaching more interactive and effective, also recorded one of the lowest standard deviations (1.26), reflecting

not only the strongest average agreement but also the most uniform consensus among respondents on this point. Similarly, the item on improving classroom participation recorded the same standard deviation (1.26), indicating comparable consistency of opinion. The item on promoting creativity and collaboration, while equally highly rated in terms of mean score, recorded the highest standard deviation (1.29) among the five items, suggesting slightly more variability in how respondents perceived this particular benefit. Together, these findings affirm the central thrust of this study's second objective: that performative pedagogy is not merely an innovative strategy in theory, but one that is practically recognised by educational practitioners in Kontagora Local Government Area as capable of meaningfully improving both the quality of instruction and the depth of student engagement.

Discussion of Findings

The findings on objective one revealed a negative and insignificant relationship between the identified challenges and the implementation of performative pedagogy in secondary schools in Kontagora Local Government Area. The respondents generally disagreed that factors such as inadequate teacher training, overcrowded classrooms, lack of instructional materials, examination-oriented teaching, and poor institutional support significantly hinder the implementation of performative pedagogy. This finding implies that although these challenges exist within the school system, they may not strongly prevent teachers from applying performative teaching strategies in classroom instruction. The result suggests that some teachers still integrate learner-centered and interactive approaches despite institutional and structural limitations. The finding aligns with the view of Gallagher and Booth,(2003) who argued that performative pedagogy can still thrive in constrained environments when teachers demonstrate creativity and adaptability in instructional delivery. However, the finding contradicts Ogunyemi, (2018) who maintained that inadequate resources and rigid curricular systems significantly impede innovative teaching practices in Nigerian schools. The implication of the finding is that teachers in the study area may have developed coping strategies that enable them to apply performative methods regardless of the identified challenges. Overall, the result indicates that the perceived challenges do not constitute a major barrier to the implementation of performative pedagogy in the selected secondary schools.

The findings of objective two revealed a positive and significant relationship between performative pedagogy and improved teaching effectiveness and student learning outcomes in secondary schools in Kontagora Local Government Area. The respondents strongly agreed that performative pedagogy improves classroom participation, enhances students' critical thinking ability, increases academic performance, promotes creativity and collaboration, and makes teaching more interactive and effective. This finding demonstrates that performative pedagogy is widely perceived as an effective learner-centered instructional approach capable of improving students' understanding and engagement during classroom activities. The result supports the constructivist position of Dewey, (1938) who emphasized that active participation and experiential learning improve educational outcomes. The finding also agrees with Bamgbose and Salawu, (2021), whose study established that role-play and simulation techniques significantly enhance students' critical thinking and academic achievement in Nigerian secondary schools. The implication of this finding is that the adoption of performative pedagogy can transform classroom teaching and learning by making students more active, creative, and academically productive. Therefore, the study concludes that performative pedagogy possesses strong prospects for improving the quality of secondary education in the study area.

Conclusion

The identified challenges, including inadequate teacher training, overcrowded classrooms, lack of instructional materials, examination-oriented teaching, and poor institutional support, have a negative but insignificant relationship with the implementation of performative pedagogy in secondary schools in Kontagora Local Government Area. Although these challenges exist within the school system, they do not significantly prevent teachers from applying performative teaching strategies. The finding suggests that teachers still attempt to integrate interactive learning approaches despite institutional limitations. The study, therefore concludes that performative pedagogy has a positive and significant relationship with improved teaching effectiveness and student learning outcomes in secondary schools in Kontagora Local Government Area, and also established that performative pedagogy enhances classroom participation, critical thinking, academic performance, creativity, and

collaboration among students. Therefore, performative pedagogy possesses strong prospects for improving the quality of teaching and learning in secondary schools.

Recommendations

- School administrators and educational stakeholders should provide continuous professional development programmes to strengthen teachers' knowledge and skills in performative pedagogy.
- Government should also improve classroom facilities and instructional resources to support innovative teaching practices. In addition, schools should encourage flexible teaching methods that promote active student participation despite existing institutional challenges.
- Teachers should be encouraged to adopt performative pedagogy more actively in classroom teaching to enhance students' participation, creativity, and academic performance.
- Educational policymakers should integrate learner-centered and performance-based instructional strategies into secondary school curricula and teacher training programmes.
- Furthermore, school management should provide supportive learning environments that promote interactive and collaborative teaching practices in secondary schools.

References

- Adeyemi, K., & Okebukola, P. (2019). Drama-based instructional strategies and students' academic achievement in English language in Nigerian secondary schools. *Journal of Language and Educational Studies*, 14(2), 44–58.
- Akinsanoye, K. E. (2025). Enhancing education delivery through constructivist learning strategy. *Journal of Theoretical and Empirical Studies in Education*.
- Akinsola, I. (2024). Theatre-in-education packages and secondary students' knowledge of Yoruba orature in Ibadan metropolis. *African Journal of Teacher Education*, 13(3), 169–191.
<https://doi.org/10.21083/ajote.v13i3.7926>
- Apata, S. B. (2023). Technological pedagogy content knowledge: Implications for English language teaching and learning in Nigerian secondary schools. *Ife Journal of Theory and Research in Education*, 24.
- Asuquo, E. N., Bassey, A. E., Onasanya, T. O., & Agbor, R. B. (2024). Nigerian senior secondary school students' engagements of digital technologies for learning. *International Journal of Innovative Technology Integration in Education*, 7(1).

Bamgbose, A., & Rasheed, S. (2021). Role-play and simulation strategies as predictors of students' critical thinking skills in civic education in Ogun State, Nigeria. *African Journal of Educational Research*, 18(1), 66–79.

Dewey, J. (1938). *Experience and education* (pp. 25–30). Macmillan.

Gallagher, K., & Booth, D. (2003). *How theatre educates: Convergences and counterpoints with artists, scholars, and advocates* (pp. 110–130). University of Toronto Press.

Ibrahim, M., & Abdul, M. (2022). Challenges and prospects of innovative teaching methods in science education in Northern Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Science and Educational Development*, 11(3), 91–105.

Odeh, C., & Eze, N. (2020). Teachers' perceptions and readiness towards the adoption of performative pedagogy in social studies teaching in Nigeria. *International Journal of Social Science and Education*, 9(4), 72–85.

Ogunkunbi, O. O., & Adejare, A. K. (2025). Improvisation in theatre-in-education: A critical review of pedagogical practices and performative learning. *International Journal of Education, Social and Management Sciences*, 1(1), 45–57.

Ogunyemi, B. (2018). Teaching and learning in Nigerian secondary schools: Challenges and prospects. *Journal of Educational Development*, 12(2), 45–60.

Olaifa, A. S., Ciroma, U. A., Olaifa, E. O., Onikoyi, O. A., & Shittu, A. A. (2025). Teachers' professional development and students' academic achievement in public senior secondary schools in Niger State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Universal Education*, 3(1).

Onyekwelu, R. A. (2024). Enhancing the quality of secondary education through professional development of teachers in Nigeria. *British Journal of Multidisciplinary and Advanced Studies*, 5(1), 194–205.

Piaget, J. (1970). *Science of education and the psychology of the child*. Orion Press.

Universal Basic Education Commission. (2024). *Basic education sector reports*.

Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in society: The development of higher psychological processes* (pp. 84–90). Harvard University Press.